

New European Bauhaus Academy

PulseArt: Cultural Awareness and Expression for inclusion and Civic Participation

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

Barcelona, February 27, 2026

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Science for Change

Circular Bio-based Europe
Joint Undertaking

PULSE-ART: Developing Cultural Awareness and Expression for Inclusion and Civic Participation

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PULSE-ART

***Promoting Understanding and Lifelong learning
Successful Education through the ARTs and culture***

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference — February 27th, 2026

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the European Union**

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The Problem

Western Societies polarisation and radicalisation, while many young citizens feel disconnected from formal education methods and don't see themselves reflected in what or how they learn.

(One of) The Gap(s)

92% of EU Member states
prioritize cultural diversity.

Only 33% report culture is well
integrated into education.

European Commission. (2025). Summary of consultation activities
accompanying the Communication on a Culture Compass for Europe.
<https://culture.ec.europa.eu/policies/culture-compass>

Cultural Awareness and Expression (CAE)

CAE means to:

- RECOGNIZE
- RESPECT
- SHARE

Worldviews
+
Identity

Key competence since
2006...
But largely invisible in
practice

Why It Matters

CAE

CO-CREATION

+

PARTICIPATION

+

DEMOCRACY

Our Response

PULSE-ART: Arts-based Methods

- Reflection
- Dialogue
- Meaning-making
- Co-creation

Towards Resilient Communities

Embedding art in education:

MOSAIC Hubs

Local cross-sector Hubs for co-creating inclusive and creative educational models

7 Communities

CASE STUDIES:

- Game Jams (Malta)
- Video Games (France)
- Performance (Netherlands)
- Science Illustration (Spain)
- Dance (Latvia)
- Visual Tech-Art (Greece)
- Music (Morocco)

Art

Professional Development Programme

TEACHING
WITH
CREATIVITY

6 training modules
for educators,
trainers, and lifelong
learning providers

Self-Reflection Tool

SELF-REFLECTION TOOL

Identifies competences'
strengths and weaknesses
of educators

And connects them with corresponding
training modules

The Observatory

Observatory for Arts in Education:

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME

BEST PRACTICES

RESOURCES

CASE STUDIES INSIGHTS

POLICY DOCUMENTS

SELF-REFLECTION TOOL FOR LEARNERS **AND** TRAINERS

Building Networks

WE CONNECT DIVERSE COMMUNITIES:

YOUTH
EDUCATORS
ARTISTS
RESEARCHERS
POLICYMAKERS

building partnerships between
educational and cultural institutions

Evidence from Practice

7 CASE STUDIES

+

1 UMBRELLA METHODOLOGY

How arts foster
CULTURAL AWARENESS
AND EXPRESSION...

- IDENTITY AWARENESS
- MUTUAL TRUST
- CREATIVE EXPRESSION
- COLLECTIVE BUILDING

RESILIENT SOCIETY

Measuring Impact

Co-created qualitative and quantitative methods

Collective reflection and iteration

Co-validation of data

Research results

Transferability of Methodologies

Informing policy with co-creation:

EU-level Policy Brief

(soon to be published)

7 National Action Plans

EU policy
recommendations

Building bridges

PULSE-ART breaks down silos between...

- EDUCATION, CULTURE, SCIENCE
- FORMAL & NON-FORMAL LEARNING
- PRACTICE, SCIENCE AND POLICY
- LEGITIMATE AND LESS RECOGNIZED ART FORMS

connecting what is
artificially separated

PULSE-ART and the New European Bauhaus

PART OF THE

**New
European
Bauhaus**

We foster:
beautiful,
sustainable,
and inclusive
learning

**WHICH MAKES
FUTURE SOCIETIES
MORE...**

PULSE-ART contributes to building skills for the NEB's growth

Designing and testing:

- Open training methodologies
- Educator capacity across Europe and beyond
- Platform to connect and inform
- Assessment tools

Skills for
integrating

Art

Sustainability

Inclusion

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

Let's make society more human, creative, and inclusive through the power of art in education!

pulseartproject.eu

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